

A SYSTEMATIC REVIEW OF THE ROLE OF LEARNING MANAGEMENT SYSTEMS IN VIRTUAL CLASSROOM INSTRUCTION DELIVERY, MANAGEMENT, AND EVALUATION IN TERTIARY INSTITUTION

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Abstract

The learning management system has been the easiest means for: tracking students' development and progress in learning; keeping records of students' performance; facilitating classroom instruction with interactive audio/visual devices that enhance deep understanding of the subject matter; accessing relevant information within a fraction of a second; communicate with colleagues via forums, to mention but a few. The study investigated factors influencing adoption, attitude and satisfaction of LMS, acceptance of LMS, perception of LMS and usefulness for classroom and online instruction. The study adopted a systematic review of related literature between 2005 and 2018. In this review, researchers are purely interested in only recently published peer-reviewed articles on learning management systems, electronic education, and electronic learning. The outcome reveals that globally, educational institutions are patronising LMS as a means of executing teaching and learning tasks, physically and/or virtually. There is a high level of satisfaction indicated by the respondents of many studies. Lastly, users saw the usefulness of the LMS, especially during the COVID-19 lockdown period.

Keywords: Learning Management System, Classroom Instruction, Virtual learning, Evaluation

Introduction

Learning has become so crucial that many institutions all over the world strive to ensure effective understanding of the content of instruction. It is commonly assumed that society judges the

effectiveness of educational institutions based on the ability, skills, and attitude of their graduates. In order to facilitate learning in a university classroom, teachers must modify their instructional approach from a simple lecture-based approach to an e-Learning based model as more tasks involve human-computer interaction, and

computer knowledge and skills have become more positively correlated with both occupational and personal success (Teo, 2008). This millennium is the era where information technology dominated educational advancements and enhanced effectiveness in teaching and learning. Electronic education (e-Learning) and Learning Management Systems (LMS) evidently contribute to the fulfilment of the dreams of many pedagogues, cyberneticists, and theorists in this millennium (Cápay & Tomanová, 2010), for which over 60 countries have adopted the LMS (Chung, Pasquini, & Koh, 2013).

With the establishment of Tertiary Education Trust Fund (TETFund) in 2008, the Nigerian Universities today have the latest technological resources that facilitate classroom instructions in the higher institutions. Whether used effectively or technically for teaching and learning purposes, many teachers are continually using the traditional method to deliver their instructions in the lecture rooms. However, most universities all over the world, ranked from 1 to 1000, make use of LMS to facilitate classroom instruction, monitor students' development attendance, keep students' records, and give access to e-Learning resources. E-Learning is defined by Cápay and Tomanová (2010) as the delivery of educational and training programmes via the Internet and/or Intranet. It can also be defined as a mixture of content (online courses or courseware) and communication (reaching online, emails, discussion forums). The use of the Internet in educational processes has evidently simplified study materials and distribution and has improved communication between the students and the teacher. e-Learning comprises instruction delivered through all kinds of electronic media, including the Internet, intranets, extranets, websites, satellite broadcasts, software applications, audio/video tapes, and interactive TV. The entire efforts made to implement e-

Learning will, in due course, move towards overall automation of administrating the processes of teaching and learning by means of a software known as Learning Management Systems (LMS), as indicated in Figure 2.1.

Figure 1: The conceptual framework for designing and developing LMS for the study

The LMS is an interactive medium that makes the most of the world wide web and technological tools that are either electronic or web-appropriated or web-fit for the purposes of teaching and learning (Haghparsat, Nasaruddin, & Abdullah, 2014). It attempts to advance more extensive appropriations in the learning environment, thereby providing access to the modelling ways to deal with classroom instructions and research communities (Aliyu, Talib, & Ali, n.d.). Moreover, it allows the teachers and students to manage the content of instruction. Hence, the name "learning management system". The teacher can easily design a planned lesson, as well as its activities and assessments, while the students enrolled in the class have access to learning resources, which they can store, download, respond to, perform, and even share with the other community. Sakai is simply an online active learning platform that engages its users in more advanced inquiry and collaborations where resources are sufficiently relevant and available. It is a

system of delivering educational content and training programs.

A Learning Management System (LMS) is a medium through which computer tools or technological devices are used to "give students strengths, motivation, and new experience in gaining knowledge" (Halim, Ali, Junaidi, & Yahaya, 2010). Through LMS, teachers would be able to effectively link the conceptual information to real-world experience. It enables teachers to learn and teach efficiently, thereby actively engaging their students in developing a deep understanding of the subject matter as well as maintaining interest throughout the lesson. Many studies have confirmed the effectiveness of LMS in improving e-Learning when compared to traditional methods used in universities for various courses such as Biology, Chemistry, Physics, and Mathematics (Aliyu, 2018; Halim et al., 2010).

Teachers could manage their courses online and create, add, modify, customize, and reuse digital content and learning objects to meet the learning objectives (Kakasevski, Mihajlov, Arsenovski, & Chungurski, 2008). The LMS emphasises the central role of computer-based technologies (e-Learning systems) in focusing on facilitating flexibility, enhancing instructions, and transforming the way individuals learn (Wu, Tennyson, & Hsia, 2010). It considers the learning materials' content, communication between learners and teachers, and communication between learners and their peers, as well as the construction of the learners' sense of place and direction within the activities that denote the learning environment. This is an important distinction because it is certainly possible to enhance regular face-to-face courses with online resources without displacing classroom contact hours. Chung, Pasquini, & Koh (2013) established that there are five categories of

features of LMS in tertiary institutions, including (i) transmitting course content; (ii) evaluating students; (iii) evaluating courses and instructors; (iv) creating class discussions; and (v) creating computer-based instruction.

Eight reasons were highlighted by Schiffman, Vignare, & Geith (2007) in a study conducted to investigate the reasons why tertiary institutions pursue e-Learning education. These reasons include: (i) attracting students from new geographic regions or student markets; (ii) contributing to extension efforts; (iii) enhancing brand; (iv) on-campus student retention; (v) providing pedagogical improvements; (vi) increasing student diversity; (vii) returning a surplus to the institution; (viii) increasing student speed to graduation; and (ix) reducing or controlling costs.

Figure 2: Descriptive Structure of Learning Management System

Today's tertiary institutions are developing learning management systems that can be used to integrate instructional material through audio, video, and text, e-mail, live chat sessions, online discussions, forums, quizzes, and assignments. Through these kinds of electronic systems, the delivery of instruction and communication between teachers and learners can be accomplished at the same time (synchronously) or at different times (asynchronously). Such systems can

enable teachers and students to be flexible in using various instructional strategies, educational technologies, interaction mechanisms or learning resources and applying them in an interactive learning environment to overcome the limitations of the classroom (Wu et al., 2010). As a result, these online learning systems may better accommodate the needs of learners or teachers who have the varying background and faced difficulty in developing a deep understanding from the traditional approach.

Beatty & Ulasewicz (2005) and Schoonenboom (2014) reported that the use of LMSs has become an integral part of higher education worldwide as teachers in tertiary institutions deliver their instructional tasks more often using a learning management system (LMS) tool than other tasks. Thus, LMSs are widely accepted and integrated into tertiary institutions all over the world (Cápay & Tomanová, 2010; Chung et al., 2013; Klobas & McGill, 2010; McGill & Klobas, 2009; and Rubin, Fernandes, Avgerinou, & Moore, 2010). Cápay & Tomanová (2010) reported that Constantine the Philosopher University in Nitra is the 4th greatest university in Slovakia and is currently using LMS Moodle as a central environment for five faculties and all departments in the institution. Moreover, Chung et al. (2013) reported that most universities and colleges in the United States of America (U.S.A.) have adopted an LMS to support instructor teaching activities and student learning processes. All instruction (all coursework is organised and paced, all learning resources (except textbooks) are accessed, all work is collected and returned, all discussion occurs, all group work takes place, and all feedback is delivered through the system) takes place through the mediation of the LMS (e.g., Blackboard, Desire2Learn) at DePaul University (Rubin, Fernandes, Avgerinou, & Moore, 2010). Finally, Hussein (2011) reported that a total of

1,283 out of 2,336, making up 55% of the courses taught at King Saud University, were offered through the learning management system.

Problem Statement

While recognising the desirability of reaching out to new students and engaging in innovative pedagogical approaches, many teachers continue to prefer traditional lectures and are sceptical about the potential for student learning in online settings (Mackeogh & Fox, 2009). Students may not find/notice their teachers' weaknesses because they dominated the classroom discussions. In this approach (the traditional method), the teachers' aim is to deliver the lesson; neither understanding nor skills are achieved/developed at the end of the instruction. Nigeria is using a standards-based system of education where standards are set for a program. The aim of the instructions is to achieve the set standards at the end of the programme that include the development of thinking skills, understanding of the subject matter, and the cultivation of higher-order thinking skills and research ability, among others. These would be difficult to achieve when tertiary institution teachers were using traditional methods in their classroom instructions. As a result, graduates from many tertiary institutions lack the necessary skills to compete with their counterparts and fit into the societal demands of the twenty-first century. Moreover, the lack of graduates with potential skills made the society and its environment underdeveloped as a result of the poor or no contribution provided by the graduates for the development of such a society.

Mackeogh & Fox (2009) reported that institutions of higher education have been criticised for offering "the same courses to the same group of academically best-qualified young students and failing

to open up to other types of learning and learners"; their approach has "slowed down innovation in curricula and teaching methods"; and that the tertiary institutions ought to be informed that they need to "grasp more directly the challenges and opportunities presented by the lifelong learning agenda." Among the crucial factors underlying the adoption of LMS include (i) the need to upskill the population to meet the challenge of the information and knowledge society and (ii) the need for accessible and flexible access to tertiary education to meet the changing nature of society and the lifelong learning agenda.

However, the increased concern about adopting LMS should be viewed in the context of the pressure on higher education systems to reorganize, modify, improve, and modernise curricula, teaching methods, expanded learning outcomes, new types of students, qualifications frameworks, quality assurance, research, and innovation (Mackeogh & Fox, 2009). Based on the studies conducted and the recommendations made, the need for integrating e-Learning in the tertiary institutions in Sokoto state is obvious. This study is intended to investigate the level of tertiary teachers' awareness of the effectiveness of e-Learning in facilitating classroom instructions, thereby demonstrating the role of LMS to the educators.

Objective of the Study

Considering the role of a learning management system in instructional delivery, classroom management, and students' progress monitoring, this study is intended to investigate:

- i. Factors that influence LMS adoption, attitude, and satisfaction

- ii. Acceptance of LMS
- iii. Perception of LMS
- iv. Usefulness for classroom and online instruction

Methodology

The study investigated factors influencing adoption, attitude and satisfaction of LMS, acceptance of LMS, perception of LMS and usefulness for classroom and online instruction. The study adopted a systematic review of related literature between 2005 and 2018. In this review, researchers are purely interested in only recently published peer-reviewed articles on learning management systems, electronic education, and electronic learning. It also considered studies that were conducted on the basis of both secondary and tertiary institutions and were written in English. Eight databases were searched, which comprise Springer, Science and Education (ELSEVIER), ERIC, SCOPUS, Web of Science, Google Scholar, and the Journal of Computer Assisted Learning. The search criteria were started with the following keywords: learning management system, LMS, electronic education, electronic learning, e-Learning, online learning, and online education. Over 620,000 results were obtained from the search engines. This result was too much for the study, and many of the articles contained irrelevant articles. All review articles, positional papers, as well as studies conducted on the premises of basic or primary education were screened out. We managed to obtain 25 results from the databases. Furthermore, articles whose titles were not aligned with the content, objectives were not clearly stated, findings did not address objectives, and the methodology was not spelled out clearly were also found. However, subsequent screening procedures continue with the titles of the articles from the results and later shift to the abstract of

those articles that have their titles qualified. After carefully reading the abstracts of those articles, only 24 qualified and were finally selected for the review indicated in Table 1.

Table 1: Review of learning management system related articles between 2005 to 2018

S.No.	Author(s)	Objectives	Participants	Method	Results
1	Klobas & McGill (2010)	To investigate the roles of student and instructor involvement in LMS success	244 students (Australian university)	Survey	Involvement was found to be important to LMS success. Student involvement was shown to have a significant effect on the benefits to students of LMS use. The more involved a student is with the LMS site for a course offering, the stronger the benefits they report obtaining from use. Instructor involvement was shown to contribute to student benefits by affecting information quality which affects the benefits students receive from use.
2	Hussein (2011)	To identify the attitudes of Faculty members at Saudi Universities towards using E-learning Management System JUSUR, which follows the National Centre for E-learning.	90	Survey	results showed a positive Attitudes of the members of the faculty at Saudi University towards E-learning management system JUSUR; no difference in attitudes towards using the system among the faculty members regarding gender or the types of colleges humanitarian, scientific and health; their needs for training in using the system and in particular learning content management and file sharing, forums, and Questions Bank.
3	Ssekakubo, Suleman, & Marsden (2011)	To identify the underlying causes of failure of LMS-supported e-learning initiatives in developing countries		Survey & Interview	The results indicated that most probable causes of failure were identified as: high ICT illiteracy rates among the student community; low comfort levels with technology; usability issues of learning management systems; poor marketing strategies; ineffective maintenance strategies and insufficient user/technical support.
4	Mackeogh & Fox (2009)	To examine the drivers and barriers which increase or decrease motivation to engage in e-learning strategies in higher education	139 teachers & 1,500 students	Mixed method	Extrinsic factors in terms of lack of time and support serve to decrease motivation and there are also fears of loss of academic control to central administration
5	Schiffman,	To analyse the reasons why	2,251	Survey	Eight of the nine reasons are found to vary in importance

	Vignare, & Geith (2007)	higher-education institutions engage in online learning	teachers		depending on the type of institution. These reasons include: (i) to get students from new geographic regions or new markets of students, (ii) to contribute to extension efforts (iii) to enhance brand (iv) on-campus student retention (v) provide pedagogic improvements (vi) increase student diversity (vii) return a surplus to institution (viii) Increase student speed to graduation and (ix) reduce or contain costs
6	Wu, Hsia, Liao, & Tennyson, (2008)	To find out whether easy to use and provide useful information have any influence on learning satisfaction. To investigate the effect of social interaction on the perceived usefulness and ease of use. To assess system functionality and content feature influence on the perceived value	376 students	Survey	The findings indicate that perceived value, perceived ease of use, and positive learning climate have a direct effect on student's learning satisfaction. The computer self-efficacy has a significant positive influence on perceived behavioural control; system functionality and content feature have a significant positive influence on perceived value; and social interaction had a significant positive influence on perceived ease of use, perceived value, and learning climate.
7	Wu, Tennyson, & Hsia (2010)	To examine the determinants of student learning satisfaction in a blended e-learning system (BELS) environment based on social cognitive theory.	212 students	Survey	The empirical findings indicate that computer self-efficacy, performance expectations, system functionality, content feature, interaction, and learning climate are the primary determinants of student learning satisfaction with BELS; Computer self-efficacy, system functionality, content feature and interaction significantly affect performance expectations. Interaction has a significant effect on learning climate.
8	Moore, Dickson-deane, & Galyen,	To find out how scholars define the learning environment	43 teachers	Mixed method	The study discovered that there was inconsistent use of terminology for different types of delivery modes. The results reveal that there are different expectations and

	(2011)				perceptions of learning environment labels: distance learning, e-Learning, and online learning
9	Kakasevski, Mihajlov, Arsenovski, & Chungurski, (2008)	To evaluation of standard modules in Moodle Learning Management System	84 students	Experiment	The results indicated that the Moodle have good usability rating for each property
10	Mcgill & Klobas, (2009)	To investigated the role of task–technology fit in LMS success, and addressed the question of how task–technology fit influences the performance impacts of LMSs.	267 students	Mixed method	The study indicated that Task–technology fit had a significant positive effect on both expected consequences of LMS use and attitude towards LMS use; expected consequences of LMS use did not influence LMS utilization in this study; instructor norms had a significant positive influence on LMS utilization; Facilitating conditions was not found to influence LMS utilization; and attitude towards LMS use had a significant positive influence on LMS utilization. And finally, the Task–technology fit had a strong positive influence on perceived impact on learning and a weak positive influence on student grades.
11	Schoonenboom, (2014)	To explain those differences, the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) perspective is missing.	180 teachers	Survey	The results show that low intention to use an LMS can be explained by (i) low task importance or performance, and/or (ii) low LMS usefulness, and/or (iii) low LMS ease of use level.
12	Horvat, Dobrota, Krsmanovic, & Cudanov, (2013)	To assess the differences in student perception of the significance of Moodle learning management system (LMS) quality characteristics and differences in student satisfaction in regard to	395 students	Survey	The results indicate that male and female students are equally satisfied with Moodle LMS quality characteristics and that there is a difference in the significance that students give to these characteristics. That there is a substantial statistical difference in the significance students gave to quality characteristics and in student satisfaction itself, according to how much time they spent using the Moodle application, which is also noted as one

		such characteristics.			of the most important aspects of the research conducted.
13	Han & Shin, (2016)	To examine factors influencing the adoption of mobile learning management systems (LMSs) and the learning effects on students' academic achievement.	1,604 students	Survey	Results showed that age and employment status were significant factors in predicting students' adoption of mobile LMSs and that there were potential connections between mobile LMS use and students' gender, age, and psychological characteristics. Result demonstrated that the use of a mobile LMS positively influenced online students' academic achievement. The findings from this empirical study present a better understanding of students' usage of mobile devices in higher education.
14	Green, Inan, & Denton, (2012)	To determine factors that influenced student satisfaction with a new learning management system and to identify which of these factors were most important.		Survey	The results indicate that usability of the LMS and availability of technical assistance is strongly correlated with student satisfaction.
15	Al-busaidi & Al-shihi, (2012)	This study examined the key factors that influence the instructors' satisfaction of LMS in blended learning, and how this satisfaction is related to their intention to continuously use LMS in blended learning and purely for distance education.	82 teachers	Survey	The findings indicated that computer anxiety, personal innovativeness, system quality, information quality, management support, incentives policy and training are key factors to instructors' satisfaction of LMS in blended learning.
16	Leeder & Lonn, (2014)	To assess academic departments and faculty users and nonusers within those departments were	404	Survey	The result showed high levels of positive perceptions of librarians, they also exhibited low awareness of the library tools and little understanding of their use

		perceptions and experience with the library tools			
17	Shin & Kang, (2015)	To investigate online students' acceptance of mobile learning and its influence on learning achievement using an information system success and extended technology acceptance model (TAM)	1,117	Survey	The result indicates that students at online universities have started to accept mobile technology as a new learning tool; consequently, its acceptance has influenced their learning achievement both directly and indirectly.
18	Wang, Woo, Quek, Yang, & Liu, (2012)	To study explores using the Facebook group as an LMS and the students' perceptions of using it in their courses	140	Survey	The results showed that students were basically satisfied with the affordances of Facebook as the fundamental functions of an LMS could be easily implemented in the Facebook group. Also, the students did not feel safe and comfortable as their privacy might be revealed
19	Weaver, Spratt, & Nair, (2008)	To investigate which areas of online teaching with Web CT needed improvement or further investigation	1314 students & 96 teachers	Survey	Opinions appear to reflect more the use of the technology made by teaching staff – students who have experienced a well-designed unit rich with resources, timely feedback and good interaction with staff reported a positive experience with the technology.
20	Emelyanova & Voronina, (2014)	To investigate the stakeholders' perceptions of the learning management system AND also the connection between perceptions and usage	109 students & 23 teachers	Survey	showed that both groups, students and teachers, are at ease with computers and using LMS is not perceived as presenting any significant difficulty for them
21	Sun, Tsai, Finger, & Chen, (2007)	To investigate the critical factors affecting learners' satisfaction in e-Learning	295	Survey	The results revealed that learner computer anxiety, instructor attitude toward e-Learning, e-Learning course flexibility, e-Learning course quality, perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, and diversity in assessments are the critical factors affecting learners'

					perceived satisfaction
22	Pituch & Lee, (2006)	To investigate the use of the e-learning system for distance education; use of the e-learning system for supplementary classroom learning; perceived usefulness of the e-learning system; and perceived ease of use of the e-learning system	259	Survey	the perceived usefulness of the e-learning system, system interactivity had the strongest direct and total effect, with the other system factors also having significant and positive total effect; perceived ease of use was also positively related to perceived usefulness
23	Raaij & Schepers, (2008)	To investigate the extent on student acceptance and use of such an e-learning system	45	Survey	Results indicate that perceived usefulness has a direct effect on VLE use. Perceived ease of use and subjective norm have only indirect effects via perceived usefulness
24	Carlos, Chiu, & Jose, (2006)	To investigate whether the e-learning continuance intention could be determined by satisfaction, which is a function of perceived quality, perceived usability, confirmation and subjective norm	18	Survey	Results suggest that users' continuance intention is determined by satisfaction, which in turn is jointly determined by perceived usefulness, information quality, confirmation, service quality, system quality, perceived ease of use and cognitive absorption

Results

The pace of learning changed for electronic media accessed online using a web-based platform called a learning management system. Table 1 describes several studies conducted on different kinds of LMS to investigate and express learning effectiveness in an online medium. Generally, authors focused on investigating factors that influence adoption of LMS, such as attitude, perception, and satisfaction of both teachers and students toward integration of LMS, acceptance of LMS by classroom teachers, and the practicality of LMS for classroom and online instruction.

Factors influencing adoption, attitude and satisfaction of LMS

Al-busaidi and Al-shihi (2012); Carlos, Chiu, and Jose (2006); Green, Inan, and Denton (2012); Han and Shin (2016); Horvat, Dobrota, Krsmanovic, and Cudanov (2013); Hussein, M. Moore, Dickson-deane, & Galyen, 2011; Schoonenboom, 2014; Sun, Tsai, Finger, & Chen, 2007; Ssekakubo, Suleman, & Marsden (20,20) Wu, Hsia, Liao, & Tennyson, (2008); Wu, Tennyson, & Hsia, (2010). reported outcomes related to influential factors concerning adoption, attitude, and satisfaction of LMS by the users (students and teachers)

The learning satisfaction is a result of the activities that the students engaged in during the teaching and learning sessions. Al-busaidi & Al-shihi (2012) reveal that LMS recorded positive responses based on user satisfaction as indicated by the findings of the study conducted by Al-busaidi & Al-shihi (2012), which indicated that computer anxiety, personal innovativeness, system quality, information quality, management support, incentives policy, and training are key

factors to instructors' satisfaction with LMS in blended learning. A similar perspective has been earlier suggested by Carlos, Chiu, & Jose (2006), that users' continued intention is determined by satisfaction, which in turn is jointly determined by perceived usefulness, information quality, confirmation, service quality, system quality, perceived ease of use, and cognitive absorption. Based on these, a conclusion was drawn from the study of Green, Inan, & Denton (2012), which reports that usability of the LMS and availability of technical assistance are strongly correlated with student satisfaction.

As a result, Schoonenboom (2014) reported that teachers' and students' low intention to use an LMS can be explained by (i) low task importance or performance, (ii) low LMS usefulness, and/or (iii) low LMS ease of use level. Moreover, to examine the determinants of student learning satisfaction in a blended e-learning system (BELS) environment based on social cognitive theory, Wu, Hsia, Liao, & Tennyson (2008) conducted a study titled "review of trends from mobile learning studies: A meta-analysis". It reveals that computer self-efficacy, performance expectations, system functionality, content feature, interaction, and learning climate are the primary determinants of student learning satisfaction with BELS; computer self-efficacy, system functionality, content feature, interaction, and interaction significantly affect performance expectations. Interaction has a significant effect on the learning climate.

Acceptance of LMS by users (students and teachers)

The level of acceptance of the LMS was studied by Leeder & Lonn, (2014); Raaij

& Schepers, (2008); and Shin & Kang, (2015). To assess academic departments and faculty users and nonusers within those departments on perceptions and experience with the library tools, Leeder & Lonn (2014) report that high levels of positive perceptions of librarians were indicated by 404 respondents, whereas they also exhibited low awareness of the library tools and little understanding of their use. Consequently, another study conducted by Raaij & Schepers (2008) to investigate the extent of student acceptance and use of such an e-learning system reveals that perceived usefulness has a direct effect on VLE use. Perceived ease of use and subjective norm have only indirect effects via perceived usefulness.

Shin & Kang (2015) investigate online students' acceptance of mobile learning and its influence on learning achievement using an information system success and extended technology acceptance model (TAM). The result reveals that students at online universities have started to accept mobile technology as a new learning tool; consequently, its acceptance has influenced their learning achievement both directly and indirectly.

Perception of LMS

Perception of LMS was studied by Carlos, Chiu, & Jose (2006); Emelyanova & Voronina (2014); Horvat, Dobrota, Krsmanovic, & Cudanov (2013); Pituch & Lee (2006); Wang, Woo, Quek, Yang, & Liu (2012). In a study conducted by Emelyanova & Voronina (2014) to investigate the stakeholders' perceptions of the learning management system and also the connection between perceptions and usage, it was found that both groups, students and teachers, are at ease with computers and using LMS is not perceived

as presenting any significant difficulty for them.

Moreover, Horvat, Dobrota, Krsmanovic, & Cudanov (2013) conducted research to assess the differences in student perception of the significance of Moodle learning management system (LMS) quality characteristics and differences in student satisfaction with regard to such characteristics. The finding of this study reveals that male and female students are equally satisfied with Moodle LMS quality characteristics and that there is a difference in the significance that students give to these characteristics. That there is a substantial statistical difference in the significance students gave to quality characteristics and in student satisfaction itself, according to how much time they spent using the Moodle application, which is also noted as one of the most important aspects of the research conducted.

Wang, Woo, Quek, Yang, & Liu (2012) conducted a survey to explore using the Facebook group as an LMS and the students' perceptions of using it in their courses. About 140 students were used as the respondents in the study. The findings reveal that students were basically satisfied with the affordances of Facebook as the fundamental functions of an LMS could be easily implemented in the Facebook group. Also, the students did not feel safe and comfortable as their privacy might have been revealed.

Usefulness for classroom and online Instruction

The usefulness of LMS for classroom and online instruction was studied by Kakasevski, Mihajlov, Arsenovski, & Chungurski, (2008); Klobas & McGill (2010); Mackeogh & Fox (2009); McGill & Klobas, (2009); Pituch & Lee, (2006); Schiffman, Vignare, & Geith (2007);

Wang, Woo, Quek, Yang, & Liu, (2012); Weaver, Spratt, & Nair, (2008); Wu, Hsia, Liao, & Tennyson, (2008). In 2009, Kakasevski, Mihajlov, Arsenovski, & Chungurski conducted a study titled "Evaluating Usability in Learning Management System Moodle" to evaluate standard modules in the Moodle Learning Management System. The study reports that the Moodle has a good usability rating for each property.

To investigate the roles of student and instructor involvement in LMS success, Klobas & McGill (2010) conducted a study titled "The Role of Involvement in Learning Management System Success." They report that involvement was found to be important to LMS success. Student involvement was shown to have a significant effect on the benefits to students of LMS use. The more involved a student is with the LMS site for a course offering, the stronger the benefits they report obtaining from its use. Instructor involvement was shown to contribute to student benefits by affecting information quality which affects the benefits students receive from use.

Conclusion

The study investigated factors influencing adoption, attitude and satisfaction of LMS, acceptance of LMS, perception of LMS and usefulness for classroom and online instruction. The outcome reveals that globally, educational institutions are patronising LMS as a means of executing teaching and learning tasks, physically and/or virtually. There is a high level of satisfaction indicated by the respondents of many studies. Lastly, users saw the usefulness of the LMS, especially during the COVID-19 lockdown period.

Reference

- Al-busaidi, K. A., & Al-shihi, H. (2012). Key factors to instructors' satisfaction of learning management systems in blended learning. *Journal of Computer High Education*, 24, 18–39. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12528-011-9051-x>
- Aliyu, H., Abdullahi, A., & Garba, A. (2021). Perceived Usefulness and Ease of Use of Learning Management System in the Delivery, Monitoring and Evaluating Virtual Classroom Instruction. *Madorawa Journal of Arts and Social Sciences (MAJASS)*, 4(1), 208–218. <https://www.majassu.com/volume-4-number-1-december-2021/>
- Carlos, J., Chiu, C., & Jose, F. (2006). Understanding e-learning continuance intention: An extension of the Technology Acceptance Model. *International Journal of Human-Computer Studies*, 64, 683–696. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhcs.2006.01.003>
- Emelyanova, N., & Voronina, E. (n.d.). *Introducing a Learning Management System at a Russian University: Students' and Teachers' Perceptions*.
- Green, L. S., Inan, F. A., & Denton, B. (2012). Examination of Factors Impacting Students Satisfaction with a new Learning Management System. *Turkish Online Journal of Distance Education-TOJDE*, 13(3), 189–197.
- Han, I., & Shin, W. S. (2016). The use of a mobile learning management system and academic achievement of online students. *Computers & Education*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2016.07.003>
- Horvat, A., Dobrota, M., Krsmanovic, M., & Cudanov, M. (2013). Student perception of Moodle learning management system: a satisfaction

- and significance analysis. *Interactive Learning Environments*, 37–41. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10494820.2013.788033>
- Hussein, H. B. (2011). Attitudes of Saudi Universities Faculty Members Towards Using Learning Management System (JUSUR). *The Turkish Online Journal of Educational Technology*, 10(2), 43–53.
- Kakasevski, G., Mihajlov, M., Arsenovski, S., & Chungurski, S. (2008). Evaluating Usability in Learning Management System Moodle. *Information Systems Management*, 613–618.
- Klobas, J. E., & McGill, T. J. (2010). The role of involvement in learning management system success. *Journal of Computing in Higher Education*, 22, 114–134. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12528-010-9032-5>
- Leeder, C., & Lonn, S. (2014). Faculty Usage of Library Tools in a Learning Management System. *College & Research Libraries*, 75(5), 641–663. <https://doi.org/10.5860/crl.75.5.641>
- Mackeogh, K., & Fox, S. (2009). Strategies for Embedding e-Learning in Traditional Universities: Drivers and Barriers. *Electronic Journal of E-Learning*, 7(2), 147–154. www.ejel.org
- McGill, T. J., & Klobas, J. E. (2009). Computers & Education A task – technology fit view of learning management system impact. *Computers & Education*, 52(2), 496–508. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2008.10.002>
- Moore, J. L., Dickson-deane, C., & Galyen, K. (2011). e-Learning , online learning , and distance learning environments : Are they the same? *Internet and Higher Education*, 14(2), 129–135. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.iheduc.2010.10.001>
- Pituch, K. A., & Lee, Y. (2006). The influence of system characteristics on e-learning use. *Computers & Education*, 47, 222–244. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2004.10.007>
- Raaij, E. M. Van, & Schepers, J. J. L. (2008). The acceptance and use of a virtual learning environment in China. *Computers & Education*, 50, 838–852. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2006.09.001>
- Schiffman, S., Vignare, K., & Geith, C. (2007). Why Do Higher Education Institutions Pursue Online Education? *Studies*, 4(5), 61–71.
- Schoonenboom, J. (2014). Using an adapted , task-level technology acceptance model to explain why instructors in higher education intend to use some learning management system tools more than others. *Computers & Education*, 71, 247–256. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2013.09.016>
- Shin, W. S., & Kang, M. (2015). The Use of a Mobile Learning Management System at an Online University and Its Effect on Learning Satisfaction and Achievement. *International Review of Research in Open and Distributed Learning*, 16(3), 110–130.
- Ssekakubo, G., Suleman, H., & Marsden, G. (2011). Issues of Adoption : Have E-Learning Management Systems Fulfilled their Potential in Developing Countries ? *South African Institute of*

Computer Scientists and Information Technologists Conference on Knowledge, Innovation and Leadership in a Diverse, Multidisciplinary Environment, 231–238.

Sun, P., Tsai, R. J., Finger, G., & Chen, Y. (2007). What drives a successful e-Learning ? An empirical investigation of the critical factors influencing learner satisfaction. *Computers & Education*.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2006.11.007>

Wang, Q., Woo, H. L., Quek, C. L., Yang, Y., & Liu, M. (2012). *Using the Facebook group as a learning management system: An exploratory study* _1195 428..438. *43(3)*, 428–439. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-8535.2011.01195.x>

Weaver, D., Spratt, C., & Nair, C. S. (2008). *Academic and student use of a learning management system : Implications for quality*. *24(1)*, 30–41.

Wu, J., Hsia, T.-L., Liao, Y.-W., & Tennyson, R. D. (2008). What determinates student learning satisfaction in a blended e-learning system environment? *PACIS 2008 Proceedings*, 149.

Wu, J., Tennyson, R. D., & Hsia, T. (2010). *Computers & Education A study of student satisfaction in a blended e-learning system environment*. *Computers & Education*, *55(1)*, 155–164. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2009.12.012>